

Software Engineering for Qualitative Data Workflows: An ethnographic Approach

From qualitative interview transcripts to FAIR research data through collaborative requirement engineering

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Summary. The presentation outlines the results of collaborative, ethnographic field and qualitative interview research with a grounded-theory-based requirement engineering and design process. This process marks the first phase of an iterative research software engineering project, which will continue with software development and collaborative user-testing. The initial requirement engineering has yielded requirements, a traceability map, and potential use cases, as well as insights into methodological approaches for research software engineering. In the process, requirements were re-contextualized to their foundational data, including field notes and interview transcripts through a traceability mapping, providing insights for use case development, feasibility, and software design. Mapping facilitates both forward and backward traceability throughout the iterative software development process, serving as a key quality criterion in software engineering. The rich context data in connection with requirement statements facilitate the development of software use cases that integrate existing research practices with existing technological solutions.

1 Background and Context

Qualitative interview transcripts are a common data type in social science and humanities (SSH) research (Simukovic 2013, 14-15; Schöpfel and Prost 2015, 100; Imeri and Danciu 2017, 10), representing unstructured text data containing sensitive information. SSH researchers have well-established research practices with this data but generally no established practice in digital data preparation for FAIR research data (Barcelona 2024, 6), including infrastructural and system requirements (Ambrasat and Heger 2020, 33; Imeri and Danciu 2017, 19-24).

2 Research Approach and Methods

This research software engineering (RSE) project addresses this gap through a user-centric, iterative design and development process (Sidadat and Song 2012, 538; Mollenhauer 2023; Mollenhauer, forthcoming). It explores researchers' demands for existing technologies while incorporating their practices to innovate technical solutions. The approach integrates ethnographic elicitation and qualitative analysis, involving researchers and their methodologies to improve RSE practice and develop usable technical solutions. The software is developed in accordance with de-RSE e.V. aims¹ of open and FAIR documentation, code, and software.

The project includes three main iterative steps: requirement elicitation, software development, and refinement through user-testing (Mollenhauer 2023; Mollenhauer, forthcoming). Initial requirements and use cases presented here are temporary and open.

The research practice incorporates discipline-specific theoretical concepts and methodologies (Marcus 2000, 9; Fischer 2006, 173; Catarci et al 2020, 2; Mollenhauer, forthcoming). Exploratory field research addressed two aspects in semi-structured interviews with data stewards, whose consulting bridges gaps between system and user:

1. How is your consulting process structured regarding user questions, issues, and practices related to existing and desired technologies?
2. What is the process of FAIR data preparation for interview transcripts, from your perspective?

Grounded-theory-based analysis of field notes from participatory field research and interview transcripts used iterative open and axial coding, generating categories that spanned all processing steps (Truschkat, Kaiser-Belz, and Volkmann 2011, 368; Corbin and Strauss 1990). To allow iterative requirement elicitation through traceability², a table maps each requirement to its category, which itself is mapped to each coded segment of data (Fig. 1) (Mollenhauer, forthcoming).

¹ "de-RSE.org – Aims" <https://de-rse.org/en/aims.html> (accessed 17 July 2025)

² "Requirements Traceability (RT) involves documenting and tracking the life of a requirement from its origin to artifacts based on it" (Mucha 2023, 4).

Code book		
Coded segment	Category 1	Requirement 1 Requirement 2
Coded segment		
Coded segment	Category 2	Requirement 3

Fig. 1. Requirement traceability mapping

3 Results

The requirement analysis yields functional (FR) and non-functional requirements (NFR) that are formulated abstractly with distinct functionalities (Halaweh 2012, 27; ISO/IEC/IEEE 2018, 15-16). Abstract formulations ensure that the software engineer must return to the “thick descriptions” (Ponterotto 2006, 539) of the initial data to carry out all iterations. Initially, 18 functional and 3 non-functional requirements were formulated for all data processing steps.

3.1 Use case evaluation

Coding was reiterated with a focus on the steps of de-identification and encryption along a more detailed process model (Halaweh 2012, 28-30) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. color-coded, use-case specific data processing steps

While other steps were discussed more often, technological and user readiness was consensually attributed only to encryption, as there was dissent on metadata standards and adequate de-identification. The reiterative analysis facilitated an assessment of use case applicability bringing the final focus on encryption.

3.2 Use-case specific requirements

The FRs relevant to software development to support qualitative interview transcript encryption include:

FR 7 – The software shall provide information on the level of GDPR-compliance achieved.

FR 8 – The software shall provide options for sensitive data encryption.

Additional requirements not specific to encryption include:

FR 6 – The software shall make use of open data formats.

NFR 1 – The integration of the software by administrators shall be easy and non-disruptive

NFR 2 – The software frontend graphic depiction shall be adjustable for additional future uses.

NFR 3 – The software shall be extensible regarding the processing steps that it includes for any additional use cases that may arise.

3.3 Software design

The data suggests initial implementation within open-source repository software commonly used at German universities. The encryption tool must be part of a collaborative, hybrid process (see Fig. 3) that includes accessible data steward consultation, allowing for scalable support and increased FAIR data processing that raises awareness of digital encryption while satisfying researchers' need for data and source security.

Fig.3. Process model of hybrid encryption support for sensitive text data

Both aspects are feasible within the context of this project (“project scoping” Cooper 2006, 26), where a technical assessment (ibid.) deems technologies and a partnership network accessible, as these have been established through the collaborative research process. Researchers are aware of their data's sensitivity but lack digital practices; this gap can be bridged by embedding support directly into the infrastructure and process.

4 Outlook, methodological implications and future use cases

The prototype to be developed within existing university technical and personnel infrastructures, can improve practices of secure handling of sensitive data while allowing researchers to publish metadata to their research data. It aims to bridge the gap between safer and more FAIR

digital data practice for sensitive personal research material in the humanities. Requirements are embedded and contextualized in a field mapping based on multi-sited ethnographic research (Marcus 1995) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4.: Multi-sited mapping of information sources.

This supports transparency (Vicente-Saez and Martinez-Fuentes 2018, 432) by depicting data sources in connection with requirement analysis data, which remains available for the development of use cases (Würfel et al 2016). It has thus revealed a potentially future use case for data de-identification combining the ethnographic practice of composite characters (Sieferle 2023; Yim and Schwartz-Shea 2021; Willis 2019) with approaches of synthetic data generation from computer and medical sciences (Gadotti et al 2024; Murtaza et al 2023). This constitutes “innovation in the design process” (Catarci et al 2020, 2), as it is revealed only through a methodological blend within embedded field research.

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